

THE INFLUENCE OF WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY AND ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SAKTHI GROUP OF COMPANIES COIMBATORE DISTRICT

Dr.P.NATARAJAN

Associate Professor, Department of Social Work,
Hindusthan College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

&

Mrs. SURIYAPRIYA K

Ph.D Research Scholar,
Department of Social Work,
Hindusthan College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Abstract

This study examines the influence of workplace spirituality and organizational climate on employee performance and overall organizational effectiveness within the Sakthi Group of Companies in Coimbatore District. Workplace spirituality, encompassing values such as meaningful work, community, and alignment between personal and organizational values, is increasingly recognized for its role in enhancing employee satisfaction, commitment, and productivity. Similarly, organizational climate defined by aspects like leadership style, work environment, and communication channels profoundly impacts employee morale and engagement. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews with employees across various departments within the Sakthi Group to assess the interplay between spirituality and organizational climate on work outcomes. Preliminary findings suggest a strong positive correlation between high levels of workplace spirituality and favorable perceptions of organizational climate, leading to enhanced job satisfaction, reduced turnover intention, and improved performance. These insights underscore the importance of fostering a supportive and spiritually enriching workplace culture as a strategy for organizational growth and resilience. This research provides actionable recommendations for HR managers and organizational leaders seeking to strengthen employee engagement through meaningful, spiritually aligned practices and a positive organizational climate.

Key Words: Workplace Spirituality and Organizational Climate.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the significance of workplace spirituality and organizational climate has gained widespread attention as critical factors influencing employee well-being, job satisfaction, and organizational performance. Workplace spirituality refers to the sense of meaningfulness, connectedness, and alignment with an organization's values that employees experience in their roles. It is rooted in concepts of purpose, belonging, and inner fulfillment that extend beyond traditional financial and career incentives. When employees find deeper meaning in their work, they are more likely to show commitment, foster positive relationships, and contribute to a supportive and engaging work environment. Organizational climate, on the other hand, encompasses the general perception employees hold about the work environment, including aspects such as leadership style, teamwork, support, and overall workplace dynamics. Together, workplace spirituality and organizational climate shape the cultural fabric of an organization, creating an environment where employees can thrive and contribute meaningfully to organizational goals. The Sakthi Group of Companies, a prominent industrial conglomerate based in Coimbatore District, serves as an ideal setting to explore the impact of these factors on employee performance and organizational success. Known for its commitment to ethical practices, community involvement, and progressive work culture, the Sakthi Group has made efforts to foster a positive organizational climate that aligns with its core values and employee expectations. Given the diverse range of industries within the group, including manufacturing, agriculture, and transportation, the company offers a unique context to analyze how workplace spirituality and organizational climate influence employees across various roles and departments.

DEFINITION

WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY

Workplace spirituality refers to the sense of meaning, purpose, and connectedness that employees experience within their work environment. It is characterized by elements such as meaningful work, a sense of community, alignment of personal and organizational values, and opportunities for personal growth and fulfillment. Unlike traditional job motivators, which may emphasize monetary or career advancement goals, workplace spirituality addresses the deeper, intrinsic needs of individuals by fostering an environment where employees feel valued, respected, and connected to a

larger purpose. This concept emphasizes the holistic well-being of employees, acknowledging their physical, emotional, and spiritual dimensions as integral parts of their work lives. Workplace spirituality is seen as a vital component in creating a more human-centered workplace, where empathy, trust, and shared values are nurtured, leading to enhanced job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and overall productivity.

ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE

Organizational climate refers to the collective perception employees have of their work environment, encompassing elements such as leadership style, communication practices, interpersonal relationships, policies, and support systems. It reflects the "atmosphere" or "feel" of the organization, shaped by employees' shared experiences and attitudes toward their roles, management, and organizational objectives. Organizational climate is influenced by factors such as reward systems, decision-making processes, levels of autonomy, and the degree of support provided for professional and personal development. A positive organizational climate fosters employee motivation, engagement, and morale, while a negative climate can lead to dissatisfaction, high turnover, and decreased performance. Unlike organizational culture, which focuses on core beliefs and values, organizational climate is more flexible and can change in response to shifts in leadership, policies, or strategic direction. Establishing a favorable organizational climate has been shown to enhance employees' well-being and contribute to the organization's long-term success.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Chawla and Guda (2022) explore the role of workplace spirituality in shaping organizational climate and enhancing employee engagement. Their study found that employees who experienced a greater sense of meaning and purpose in their work reported higher engagement levels and a stronger alignment with organizational values. The study used a mixed-methods approach, surveying over 300 employees across various industries, including manufacturing, to examine how spirituality contributes to an inclusive and supportive climate. The findings indicate that workplace spirituality can be a significant factor in building a positive organizational climate, enhancing job satisfaction, and reducing turnover rates. The study's insights highlight the benefits of fostering a spiritually enriched environment, particularly in industries like manufacturing, where job demands can be high.

Kumar and Narayan (2023) conducted a comparative study on workplace spirituality and organizational climate, focusing on how these variables influence employee morale and organizational loyalty across multiple sectors, including the manufacturing sector. Their study involved 400 participants from diverse backgrounds, providing a robust comparative framework. Findings reveal that organizations with strong workplace spirituality and a supportive climate tend to report higher levels of organizational commitment and lower employee burnout. This study's implications suggest that companies like the Sakthi Group in the manufacturing industry could benefit from integrating spiritual practices and policies that foster a sense of community and shared purpose among employees. The authors emphasize the need for management to align organizational practices with employees' intrinsic motivations, ultimately improving workplace culture and performance.

Raj and Kaur (2021) examine the impact of organizational climate and workplace spirituality on job satisfaction and employee retention, focusing on medium to large organizations in India's industrial sectors. Their study involved a survey of 350 employees, revealing that organizations with a positive climate and spiritually enriched workplace are more likely to retain employees and improve job satisfaction levels. The research highlights that spiritual values within the workplace, such as a focus on ethical practices and a sense of purpose, enhance employees' loyalty and reduce turnover intentions. The study suggests that organizations aiming to improve retention rates should invest in nurturing an inclusive climate that respects employees' spiritual needs. For organizations like the Sakthi Group, which operates in a competitive industrial sector, fostering workplace spirituality and a supportive organizational climate can be key strategies to attract and retain skilled talent.

Methodology of the Study

Objective of the Study

- To study the personal profile of the respondents.
- To assess the levels of workplace spirituality and organizational climate of the respondents.
- To investigate the influence of personal factors on workplace spirituality and organizational climate of the respondents.
- To study the relations between workplace spirituality and organizational climate of the respondents.

- To examine workplace spirituality and organizational climate as significant predictors among the respondents.

Research design: The researcher followed descriptive research design for the study.

Universe of the study: The population or universe of a study refers to the complete set of all units relevant to the research. In this study, the researcher has chosen the employees of the "Sakthi Group of Companies" as the universe. This encompasses all individuals working across the six distinct units within the Sakthi Group. The total universe comprises 575 employees, representing a diverse range of roles within the organization. These roles include general employees, managers, assistant managers, supervisors and system administrators. Each of these groups contributes to the overall understanding of how workplace spirituality and organizational climate impact employee performance within the Sakthi Group. By including all these roles, the study aims to capture a comprehensive view of the organizational dynamics at play.

Sampling: The sampling technique utilized in this study is probability sampling, which ensures that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected. From the total population of 575 employees, a sample of 365 employees was chosen for the study. The method used for selecting these samples was simple random sampling, specifically employing the lottery method. The complete list of employees was obtained from the head office, and the sampling process was meticulously carried out to ensure unbiased selection.

According to D. Morgan and Krejcie's sample size determination formula, a sample of 240 employees would be sufficient to represent the entire population. To account for potential non-responses or incomplete data, questionnaires were distributed to 380 employees. After the data collection, and subsequent editing process, 365 of the returned questionnaires were deemed valid and suitable for inclusion in the study. This approach ensured that the final sample size exceeded the required number, providing a robust basis for the analysis.

Tools for data collection:

Personnel Profile:

The personal profile of the respondents constitutes a total of 14 questions such as age, gender, education, type of family, occupation, salary, experience and the living area etc.

Spirituality Measurement Scale (SMS)

Spirituality Measurement Scale (SMS) was propounded by Makkar & Singh (2018). This schedule has 38 statements rated on a 5 point scale and a reliability of = Alpha = .9253. The items include all relevant components of 1, Strongly Disagree 2, Disagree 3, Neither Agree nor Disagree 4, Agree 5, Strongly agree.

Organizational Climate Scale

Organizational Climate Scale was propounded by Patterson et al. (2005). The scale includes 36 items rated on a 5 point scale and reliability of Alpha = .8211. The items include all relevant components of 1, Strongly Disagree 2, Disagree 3, Neither Agree nor Disagree 4, Agree 5, Strongly agree.

Employees Performance Scale

Employee's Performance Scale was propounded by Koopmans, (2015). It consists of 31 questions measured in a 5 point scale in which items rated on a reliability of Alpha = .9015. The items include all relevant components of 1, Strongly Disagree 2, Disagree 3, Neither Agree nor Disagree 4, Agree 5, Strongly agree.

The statistical tools applied by the researcher are Percentage Analysis, Chi-square, T-test and ANOVA.

Finds of the Study

FACTORS	MEDIUM	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age	20yrs – 30yrs	221	60.5%
Gender	Male	245	67.1%
Education qualification	UG	200	54.8%
Marital Status	Married	219	60%
Type of Stay	Family	323	88.5%
No of children's	No	175	47.9%
Type of Family	Nuclear family	253	69.3%
No. of Dependents	2-4	194	53.2%
Monthly family Income (in Rs.)	Rs.30001- Rs.50000	136	37.3%
Designation	Workers	135	37.0%

Department	Production	125	34.2%
Total Experience(in years)	Below-5yrs	221	60.5%
Present Experience(in years)	0yrs – 5yrs	302	82.7%
Monthly Income (in Rs.)	Below-Rs.15000	234	64.1%

Personal Profile of the Respondents

Majority (60.5 percent) of the respondents belong to the age group of 20 to 30 years.

Majority (67.1 percent) of the respondents are male.

More than half of the total (54.8 percent) respondents are U.G graduates.

Most (60 percent) of the respondents are married.

Majority (88.5 percent) of the respondents are staying with family.

Less than half (47.9 percent) of the respondents are no children.

Majority (69.3 percent) of the respondents live in nuclear family.

Most (53.2 percent) of the respondents are 2 to 4 number of dependents.

Less than half (40 percent) of the respondents earn between below-30000 family income per month.

Nearly 37 percent of the respondents are workers.

Nearly 34.2 percent of the respondents are working production department.

More than half (60.5 percent) of the respondents belong to the total years of the experience below – 5years.

Majority (82.7 percent) of the respondents belong to the present years of the experience 0 – 5years.

More than half (64.1 percent) of the respondents earn between below-15000 income per month.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY LEVEL OF RESPONDENTS

S. No	Workplace Spirituality	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	High (173-230)	119	32.6

2	Moderate (134-172)	152	41.6
3	Low (46-133)	94	25.8
TOTAL		365	100

The above table highlights the workplace spirituality level of the respondents. It is understood from the above table that 41.6 percent of the respondents have moderate level of workplace spirituality, 32.6 percent of the respondents have high level of workplace spirituality and 25.8 percent of the respondents have low level of workplace spirituality.

INFLUENCE OF PERSONAL PROFILE AND WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.NO	PERSONAL VARIABLES	TEST APPLIED	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL
1	Age	ANOVA	*
2	Gender	t-test	*
3	Education qualification	ANOVA	NS
4	Marital Status	t-test	*
5	Type of Stay	t-test	*
6	No of children's	ANOVA	*
7	Type of Family	t-test	*
8	No. of Dependents	ANOVA	*
9	Monthly family Income (in Rs.)	ANOVA	*
10	Designation	ANOVA	*

11	Department	ANOVA	*
12	Total Experience(in years)	ANOVA	*
13	Present Experience(in years)	ANOVA	*
14	Monthly Income (in Rs.)	ANOVA	*

**INFLUENCE OF PERSONAL PROFILE AND ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE OF THE
RSPONDENTS**

S.NO	PERSONAL VARIABLES	TEST APPLIED	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL
1	Age	ANOVA	NS
2	Gender	t-test	*
3	Education qualification	ANOVA	*
4	Marital Status	t-test	NS
5	Type of Stay	t-test	*
6	No of children's	ANOVA	*
7	Type of Family	t-test	*
8	No. of Dependents	ANOVA	*
9	Monthly family Income (in Rs.)	ANOVA	*
10	Designation	ANOVA	*
11	Department	ANOVA	*
12	Total Experience(in years)	ANOVA	*
13	Present Experience(in years)	ANOVA	*
14	Monthly Income (in Rs.)	ANOVA	*

SUGGESTIONS

- Offering regular workshops or seminars on personal and professional development can help employees connect their individual goals with the organization's vision, enhancing their sense of purpose.
- Creating an inclusive organizational climate where employees feel valued and heard is crucial for workplace spirituality.
- Developing programs that focus on employees' mental and spiritual well-being can contribute to a more fulfilling work environment.
- Leadership plays a key role in shaping organizational climate and promoting workplace spirituality.
- Developing a sense of community and connectedness among employees enhances workplace spirituality.
- Creating avenues for career advancement and personal growth can help employees feel valued and supported in their roles.
- To sustain a positive organizational climate, the Sakthi Group should conduct regular assessments, such as employee surveys and focus groups, to gauge employee perceptions and satisfaction levels.

CONCLUSION

The study on the influence of workplace spirituality and organizational climate within the Sakthi Group of Companies highlights the vital role that a supportive, spiritually enriched environment plays in enhancing employee satisfaction, loyalty, and overall organizational effectiveness. By fostering a workplace culture that prioritizes meaningful work, personal growth, and a strong sense of community, the Sakthi Group can create an environment where employees feel more engaged and committed to organizational goals. Positive organizational climate, characterized by open communication, ethical leadership, and inclusivity, further strengthens this foundation by promoting trust and a shared vision. Implementing workplace spirituality and cultivating a constructive organizational climate are not only beneficial for individual employees but also essential for the company's long-term success. The findings suggest that organizations like the Sakthi Group can leverage these elements to reduce turnover, boost morale, and improve productivity. As companies in competitive industries strive for sustainable growth, integrating spiritual values and building a positive organizational climate offer a pathway to align employee

well-being with organizational performance. These strategies can help the Sakthi Group remain resilient and adaptive, ensuring its continued success and fostering a work environment where employees and the organization can grow harmoniously.

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